

**Multi-Mode Feedback in Large
Writing Classrooms at Antonine
University (Beirut, Lebanon)
Presented by Nina Kang**

Multi-Mode Feedback in Writing Classrooms

April 22, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom	Foundations of Assessment in Language Teaching / Principles of Metacognition
April 29, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom	Whole Class Feedback: Identifying Common Mistakes with a Focus on Grammar & Mechanics
May 6, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom	Peer Feedback: Targeted Tasks & Discussions
May 13, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom	Self Feedback: Showcasing Growth through Writing Portfolios & Projects
May 20, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom	Final Debriefing: Discussing Challenges & Best Practices

Agenda, Session 2

Warm-Up & Review - 10min

Presentation w Discussion - 50min

Break - 5min

Small Group Activity (breakout room) –
30 min

Wrap up - 5min

Multi-Mode Feedback in Large Writing Classrooms

Workshop Objectives:

- Learn to identify student texts appropriate for modeling feedback on content, stylistic, and grammatical issues
- Introduce and practice using multi-mode feedback strategies
- Develop strategies aimed at helping students to construct their own criteria leading to self-corrections and other self-directed skills

Review: Peer Feedback

Effective Peer Feedback

Guided (teacher led & student sustained)

Structured (with focused tasks or criteria)

Peer
Feedback
vs
Whole-Class
Feedback

Peer Feedback

Focus on Content/Genre

- Audience
- Purpose
- Organization

WCF

Focus on Language

- Grammar
- Mechanics

Best Practices

- Provide clear guidelines and require deliverables (e.g., fill out form)
- Should take place before (not after) the final version of the paper (use for revising, not editing process)
- Repeat use of peer feedback (normalize practice)
- Mix up when and who (e.g., in-class or as homework, in pairs or in small groups)
- Integrate PF tasks into grading system

Part 1: Basis for Self Feedback

Self Feedback (Self-Assessment)

The Self-Assessment offers writers an opportunity to review and reflect upon the development of their writing and communication skills and identify goals and strategies to further their development.

Meta-Cognitive Skills

- Higher-order thinking
- Control over cognitive process (develop strategies, make decisions)
- Key to becoming an independent learner (with problem-solving skills)

Self Feedback → Reflective Thinker

- To be effective with self-feedback, students need to develop their ability to think critically
- To help students learn and practice these critical thinking skills, build in time for reflection throughout their work block

Types of Self Assessment

1. Reflection-in-action, which occurs during the writing process;

2. Constructive reflection, which takes place between and among drafts, or revisions; and

3. Reflection-in-presentation, where formal self-assessment occurs.

Source: Donald Schon's *Educating the Reflective Practitioner*, 1983.

Ideas for Self-Feedback

1. Checklist
2. Rubric
3. Portfolio

1. Using a Checklist for Self Feedback

- Clearly states what needs to be included in a writing assignment
- Serves as a useful reminder of expectations and help students to stay focused on tasks
- Ensures all the key elements of a particular type of writing are included
- Can limit student errors (i.e., less instructor comments necessary)

Checklist Items

Some common checklist items include:

- An introduction that clearly states their position
- At least three reasons or examples that support the position
- Each reason developed with details and evidence
- A conclusion that summarizes their argument

Persuasive Essay Checklist

Name: _____

My topic: _____

- I clearly state my position in the introduction.
- I give at least three reasons to support my position.
- I support each reason with details and evidence.
- I stay focused on the topic.
- My conclusion summarizes my argument.

Other things I want to make sure I do:

- _____
- _____
- _____

Notes: _____

Making a Bar Graph

Name: _____

- My graph is clear and easy to read.
- My graph shows the data correctly.

Look at the sample graph. Does your graph have these elements?

- Title
- Scales
- Bars all the same width
- Labels

2. Using a Rubric for Self Feedback

A rubric:

- Details the criteria for good work
- Provides important guidelines for students in the writing process
- Can list levels of performance (e.g., numerical scores); or simply list expectations for proficient work
- Can promote “growth mindset”

Persuasive Essay Rubric

Name: _____ Essay topic: _____

	4 - Advanced	3 - Proficient	2 - Approaching	1 - Beginning
Focus/topic/opening	Strongly and clearly states a personal opinion. Introduces the main points of the opinion/argument.	Clearly names the personal opinion. Makes some reference to the main points of the opinion/argument.	Personal opinion is not clearly stated. Makes little or no reference to the main points of the opinion/argument.	Personal opinion is not easily understood. Makes no reference to the main points of the opinion/argument.
Support for position	Includes three or more reasons for the opinion and each reason is supported by evidence (facts, statistics, examples). The writer addresses potential reader concerns, biases, or arguments and has provided at least one counter-argument.	Includes three or more reasons for the opinion and each reason is supported by evidence (facts, statistics, examples).	Includes two reasons for the opinion and provides minimal evidence for each reason (facts, statistics, examples).	Includes one reason for the opinion but provides little evidence to support the reason.
Transitions	Uses a variety of transitions that clearly show how ideas are connected.	Transitions show how ideas are connected. Uses some variety in transitions.	Some transitions are used; connections between ideas are not clear.	Transitions are unclear or not present.
Closing paragraph	The conclusion leaves the reader clearly understanding the writer's opinion. Author clearly summarizes opinion/argument.	The conclusion leaves the reader understanding the writer's opinion. Author summarizes opinion/argument.	Author is not clear in summarizing opinion/argument.	There is no conclusion.
Grammar and spelling	Contains few if any errors.	Contains few errors and errors do not interfere with meaning.	Contains many errors and errors interfere with meaning.	Contains many errors that interfere with meaning and make essay illegible.

Persuasive Essay Rubric

Name: _____ Essay topic: _____

Concerns <i>Areas for improvement</i>	Criteria for Proficient Work	Advanced <i>Evidence of exceeding standards</i>
	Criteria #1: Focus/topic/opening Clearly names the personal opinion. Makes some reference to the main points of the opinion/argument.	
	Criteria #2: Support for position Includes three or more reasons for the opinion and each reason is supported by evidence (facts, statistics, examples).	
	Criteria #3: Transitions Transitions show how ideas are connected, and some variety of transitions are used.	
	Criteria #4: Closing paragraph The conclusion leaves the reader understanding the writer's opinion. Author summarizes opinion/argument.	
	Criteria #5: Grammar and spelling Contains few errors and errors do not interfere with meaning.	

3. Using a Portfolio for Self-Feedback

Portfolio is a collection of student work which shows student efforts, progress, and achievements

Key Feature #1: Student-Structured

- Students identify their strengths and weaknesses
- Students prioritize their learning needs
- Students choose topics and set goals

Key Feature #2: Reflective

- Students are asked to think about their **goals**
- Students are constantly engaged in **self-reflection**

Portfolios as Learning Process

- Goals/Objectives
- Student Performance
- Teacher & Self Feedback
- Continuous Reflection

Student Portfolio Steps

Identify learning goals/objectives

Align goals/objectives with class assignments and projects

Select student work (based on criteria)

Give feedback on student work

Ask students to reflect on progress

Make necessary changes based on observation and feedback

Portfolio Organization

Samples of what to include:

- Learner Goals
- Work samples
- Teacher Feedback
- Self-Reflection
- Rubrics

Combined Purpose Portfolios

- Showcase Portfolios: For evaluation
- Growth Portfolios: For demonstrating final performances and/or products
- Evaluation Portfolios: For demonstrating progress/growth

Types & Purposes of Portfolios

– *Showcase*

- Emphasizes **product** of learning
- Showcases end-of-year/semester accomplishments
- Highlights student perceptions of “best” work
- Communicates current aptitudes (for future courses/teachers)

Types & Purposes of Portfolios – *Evaluation*

- Documents achievement for grading/ placement
- Shows progress towards goals/standards
- Reflects on cumulative achievement

Objectives: 1 I'll write, direct, and act.		Beat 10	Met 6	Didn't 2	6
2 We'll make a short video.	It should be shorter. Part of it is boring.	Beat 10	Met 6	Didn't 2	6
3 We'll write in class and shoot in the park.		Beat 10	Met 6	Didn't 2	6
4 We need to be done in 2 weeks.	We have 2 days to go!	Beat 10	Met 6	Didn't 2	10
5 We'll show what the expansion was like for Native Americans.	We need another scene showing Tecumseh's side.	Beat 10	Met 6	Didn't 2	2
6 We'll use Mom's camera and make props/costumes.		Beat 10	Met 6	Didn't 2	6
TOTAL:					76

Types & Purposes of Portfolios – *Growth*

- Emphasizes the *process* of learning
- Tracks growth/development of performance over time
- Identifies strengths/weaknesses
- Helps develop goal-setting & self-assessment skills

♥ The Writing Process

Formal Name (stage)	What you do as a WRITER!
Prewriting	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Choose a topic• Plan it out<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Brainstorm<ul style="list-style-type: none">↳ Draw a picture (visualize)↳ senses chart
Drafting	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Put your ideas on paper• "sloppy copy"
Revising	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Re-reading and asking, "How can I make it better?"• Idea sharing (Peer Support)<ul style="list-style-type: none">* details, organization* crafting - figurative language
Editing	<ul style="list-style-type: none">* Capitals* Punctuation* Sentence Structure* Word Choice
Publishing	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Creating a final COPY• <u>Title</u> ~ Common Catchy Creative

Best Practices for Self-Feedback

- Open-ended questions prompt reflective thinking
- Reflection formats provide structure for students' thinking about their work (e.g., reflection sheets, self-evaluation forms, journals)

Student Self-Assessment (samples of students' self assessment forms)

- I want to be a more interesting writer but I keep using simple sentences and lots of repetition of words.
- I have too many semicolon but I'm not sure if I'm using it right.
- *Software* is an uncountable noun, but I said *softwares*. *I'm also confused about whether research is non-count or not*
- Sometimes I don't use third person verb correctly and I get confused about adding the s or not
- I use the same word "also" three times in one paragraph.

Part 2: Setting Up Self-Feedback Tasks

DISUSSION OF STUDENT SAMPLE (B1.2), 339 words

In Lebanon everything is different, so what can be better to university students in Lebanon ,online or on campus learning ? There is a big debate about this topic especially in Lebanon because of the country's situation and its impact on education. On campus learning is better for many reasons.

There are many reasons that gives preference to on campus learning over online learning in Lebanon for university students, one of them is that on campus, everyone can attend classes because it doesn't require internet unlike online learning where internet at home is essential. According to studies, 55% of Lebanese families after the crises are under the poverty level, so students have to work and miss classes to pay university and internet bills,without mentioning electricity crises .

Furthermore, on campus students can interact more with people , they can ask questions and get answered immediately so they can understand more , they also can have friends and build relationships , wich is so important to preserve a good mental health despite all the crises in Lebanon , while in online sessions, students are sitting hours in front of screens , they cant talk with anybody , and if they didn't understand they just leave the meeting.

There is one reason that makes online learning better than on campus learning, is the price of petrol in Lebanon. Recently , petrol tank in Lebanon costs 500 000 L.L , so students who lives far from the university will face a real issue especially with the current economic crisis unlike online learning where students can attend classes from their homes . But this can be fixed by taking a dorm in the university so they can reach it by walking.

In conclusion , on campus learning is better than online because everyone can attend sessions,students can build communities,and they can understand more.Even though in Lebanon everything seems like there is not a promising future but students should believe that they are the true revolution and with education they can change everything.

Instructor Comments on Turnitin

In Lebanon everything is different, so what can be better to university students in Lebanon, online or on campus learning? There is a big debate about this topic especially in Lebanon because of the country's situation and its impact on education. On campus learning is better for many reasons.

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6 minutes (127 words)

Whole Class Feedback (focus on verb usage)

Identify all the verbs (including auxiliaries) in the passage. Note all the repetitions and errors (e.g., verb tense, passive voice). Try rewriting to improve the passage.

Furthermore, on campus students can interact more with people , they can ask questions and get answered immediately so they can understand more , they also can have friends and build relationships , wich is so important to preserve a good mental health despite all the crises in Lebanon , while in online sessions, students are sitting hours in front of screens , they cant talk with anybody , and if they didn't understand they just leave the meeting.

Whole Class Feedback (mechanics, editing)

Edit the following passage.

Furthermore, on campus students can interact more with people by asking questions and getting answers immediately, so they can understand more. They also can have friends and build relationships , wich is so important to preserve a good mental health despite all the crises in Lebanon. In online sessions, students are sitting hours in front of screens. They cant talk with anybody , and if they don't understand they just leave the meeting.

Peer Feedback Form (Holistic)

1. What style does the writer use to introduce the paper?
2. What is the thesis statement?
3. Where is the thesis located? Does the thesis state the writer's position?
4. What is the writer arguing for or against?
5. What support (reasons) does the writer give for the thesis? State three reasons supporting the thesis.
6. Does the writer use examples or quotations to support the thesis? List three examples.
7. How does the writer conclude the essay?
8. Did the writer convince you of their position? How?
9. Name three things that you liked about this essay.
10. Give 2-3 suggestions for improving the essay.

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Self-Assessment, Checklists (Yes/No)

Does your essay meet the minimum word count requirement?	Yes	No
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Does your essay contain an original title that is attention-getting and specific?	Yes	No
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Is your essay a minimum of five paragraphs?	Yes	No
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Does your essay contain an explicit thesis statement?	Yes	No
---	-----	----

Does your essay focus on a breakdown of the literature?	Yes	No
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Is your essay formatted according to MLA style guidelines (see the syllabus)?	Yes	No
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Use of Learning Strategies

Please rate your use of each learning strategy below on a scale between 1 to 5. Circle your choice.

1=never

2=rarely

3=sometimes

4=often

5=most often

General Writing Strategies					
I often write in my native language.	1	2	3	4	5
I often write in English.	1	2	3	4	5
I write for pleasure in my <u>freetime</u> in English.	1	2	3	4	5
I write notes, messages, letters, or reports in English.	1	2	3	4	5
I use a bilingual dictionary.	1	2	3	4	5
I use an English-English dictionary.	1	2	3	4	5
I use an English grammar book or handbook.	1	2	3	4	5
I read native English writing.	1	2	3	4	5
I use the English words I know in different ways.	1	2	3	4	5

Self-Assessment Form

(Long Answers)

1. Describe your writing process for this essay. For example, did you go through the conventional steps of prewriting (brainstorming, freewriting, listing, mapping, etc.), planning (whether by an outline or otherwise), drafting, getting feedback from others, and revising, or did you take another approach?
2. Evaluate your writing process for this essay. What worked well for you? What is something you might do differently next time? What would possibly be improved by this change?
3. Using a scale of 1-10, with 1 being the worst and 10 being the best, evaluate your written product; that is, how well did the essay turn out in your view? Was it successful? Based on your evaluation of the final draft, what are its strong points? Where could it continue to be improved?

Summary Points

- There are many advantages to incorporating Self Feedback in writing (developing critical thinking skills through self reflection and creating opportunities for students to self-correct and grow through the process).
- Self Feedback is versatile tool before/during/after the writing process and can help to reduce workload for instructors by limiting unnecessary instructive comments.

Part 3: Application (Small Group Activity)

Small Group Activity

1

Break out into 2-3 groups according to level (A1 & B1.1, B1.2, B1.3).

2

Each group will be given a student sample to evaluate.

3

Brainstorm ideas on how you would structure a self feedback task? (15min)

4

Come up with 3-5 questions to add to Self Feedback form (catered to the level) and be prepared to share 2-3 ideas with the rest of the group.